

**THE IDEA AS AN EMOTIONAL-AESTHETIC FACTOR OF ARTISTRY
IN AZIZ SAID'S POEM "TIME DIMENSION"**

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Annotation

This article examines the mediating role of the idea in shaping the poet's conscious and creative attitude toward existence. It analyzes the poetic interpretation of emotional perception and philosophical generalization, the evaluation of the vitality of material existence, and the process of spiritual renewal within the framework of aesthetic cognition. The research focuses on the poem "Time Dimension" by Aziz Said, exploring the peculiarities of its artistic essence and the lyrical hero's emotional and symbolic experiences. The study also identifies and interprets the creative objectives of the poet and the distinctive features of his artistic worldview.

Keywords: idea, poetic interpretation, emotional experience, aesthetic perception, philosophical generalization, subjective intuition, author's psychology, artistic analysis.

**AZIZ SAIDNING "VAQT MANZILI" SHE'RIDA G'OYA EMOTSIONAL-
ESTETIK TA'SIRCHANLIK OMILI SIFATIDA**

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Annotatsiya

Maqolada shoir borliqqa ongli-ijodiy munosabati shakllanishida g'oya vositachilik roli, poetik talqinda hissiy idrok va falsafiy umumlashma yaxlitligi, hayotiy materialni baholashda estetik quvvat-hofiza tutgan o'rni, ongga tashqi ta'sir inertsiyasi hamda muallif dunyoqarashida qayta tiklangan mohiyat xususiyati Aziz Saidning "Vaqt manzili" she'ri timsolida tahlillanadi. Unda hayotiy kuzatish va jonli mushohada reaksiyasi, materiya va tanlov originalligi xususida fikr yuritiladi. Aslida voqelik mavhum, adabiy zavq hamda obraz taqvimi uni saralaydi, boyitadi va aniqlashtiradi, badiiy ifodada maqsad hamda vazifa birligi esa subyektiv ibtidoni tavsiflaydi.

Tayanch so'zlar: g'oya, poetik talqin, hayotiy material, tasvir, ifoda, idrok, mohiyat, mushohada, kuzatish, materiya, tanlov, estetik qiymat, baholash mezonlari, she'r, his-tuyg'u, falsafa, mantiq, badiiy umumlashma, subyektiv ibtido, shoir, muallif, ruhiyat, tahlil, originallik.

The essence of humanity is perceived through emotional cognition; emotion, excitement, desire, passion, and feeling acquire precision in the artistic idea. The image calendar essentially directs life material toward a subjective beginning, revealing the author's intention, purpose, and goal in the nuance of attitude. In this sense, "the artistic idea emerges in connection with the artist's attitude toward existence, their ability to comprehend, understand and evaluate the mysteries of nature and the social phenomena of the era, as well as their ideals of beauty, nobility and happiness. Accordingly, the image discovered through these becomes a product of the mind imbued with a particular worldview" [2:108]. In the current situation, the clarity of depiction ensures the vividness of imagination, while the passion of expression precisely directs the movement of meaning in action. Observation, comparison, proportion, simile, juxtaposition, analysis and interpretation transition

from cognitive theory to creative product:

Va bundan ikki ming yil muqaddam edi
 va shu kuni edi
 va yarim tunda yulduzlarga tikilib o'tirar
 va ularning nima ekanligini
 va o'zinning nega paydo etilganimni
 va bizni Kim qo'shiq kuylashga
 va Kim ytig'lashga majbur qilayotganini
 va muhabbat
 va nafrat qayerdan paydo bo'lishini
 anglamoqchi bo'lar [3:9].

(And it was two thousand years ago / and it was this day / and at midnight he would sit staring at the stars / and what they are / and why I came into being / and Who compels us to sing songs / and Who compels us to weep / and where love / and hatred come from / he would try to understand.)

Perceiving the beginning and end directs action toward distance; in metaphor and detail, the intensity of time is manifested. Aziz Said in his poem "Vaqt manzili" (The Destination of Time) (2000) grafts the landscapes of human psychology onto the flow of events and phenomena, enters into living dialogue with the heart, and strives to define the boundary between understanding and non-understanding in emotional cognition. During futile preoccupation, concepts materialize; the succession of generations serves to enrich experience. Philosophy and logic become means of self-expression; analytical skill brings difference, depth, and reform to the agenda. The author strives to gather human lifestyle into the measure of time; the tendency to comprehend the essence that arose "two thousand years ago" fragments human sensation, imagination, conception, observation, and possibility across the cross-section of eras. The extreme sharpness of unanswered questions (bizni Kim

qo'shiq kuylashga va Kim yig'lashga majbur qilayotganini va muhabbat va nafrat qayerdan paydo bo'lishini anglamoqchi bo'lar / who compels us to sing songs and who compels us to weep and where love and hatred come from he would try to understand) actually characterizes the comparisons taken from nature, while the creatively independent conjunction (va / and) describes the expressiveness of the utterance alongside ensuring logical consistency. A legitimate question arises at this point: where does the destination of time begin? Can humanity, whose lineage is connected to Adam and Eve, transcend the spirals of time? In the core of rhetorical questions, struggle, hope, desire, entreaty, and wonder intermingle.

The author's positive attitude toward reality reflects the individual essence of the idea; the unity of emotional cognition and evaluation criteria helps to comprehend the terminology. Life material becomes specific in poetic interpretation; problems reprocessed in the creator's nature renew expression. Accordingly, the process "from the selection of life material, how it is generalized, the hierarchical arrangement of images in artistic reality, drawing their appearance, describing their actions and behavior, depicting their conduct and psychology—in all of this, the author's subjectivity and the influence of the idea they wish to express can be felt. This very thing governs the work's reception by the reader, directing the reader to understand the work as the author wishes" [5:153]. The author's subjectivity typically organizes purpose and task; ideational governance specifies the process of information transmission and reception. The practical elaboration of themes that pass from the spirit of the era to the creator's worldview transforms real reality into artistic expression; emotion in motion elevates aesthetic value to the stage of investigation. The factor of expressive impact acquires particular weight through the poet's artistic skill; poetic images comparable to discoveries serve to evoke specific conceptions and awaken impressions:

Va men hayotni sevardim

Va o'limni sevmasdim

Va ozodlikni sevardim

Va qullikni sevmasdim [3:21].

(And I loved life / And I did not love death / And I loved freedom / And I did not love slavery.)

Through contrasting depiction (hayot va o'lim, ozodlik va qullik / life and death, freedom and slavery, peace and war, pride and humility), the poet expands scope; the nuance of affirmation-negation (sevardim-sevmasdim / I loved—I did not love) generalizes the contradiction between desire and possibility. The author creates a yesterday-today-tomorrow focus, ensuring rapid thought movements at the crossroads of psychology, condition, scene, tableau, and mood. Similes that set imagination in motion also strengthen the thread between details, depicting the nation's history echoing from the depths of the past. The creator, who has described the tragedy and achievements of "taqdir qilib bitilgan vatan" (the homeland written by fate) as if stringing them on a thread, intensifies the weight of the idea: the enemy who took "vatanni, xatni, dini, tilni, g'ururni, orni" (the homeland, script, religion, language, pride, honor) gives "qullarga nishon, sotqinlarga amal, qo'rqoqlarga yorliq, josuslarga unvon, maddohlarga martaba, raiyatga yolg'onni" (medals to slaves, positions to traitors, decrees to cowards, titles to spies, ranks to flatterers, lies to subjects). The decline of "o'z-o'ziga nish urgan chayon yanlig' bu qora saltanat" (this dark reign, a scorpion that stings itself) opens the way to Uzbekistan's independence, yet "oldingami, orqagami shitob bilan suzayotgan vaqt manzili" (the destination of time floating swiftly forward or backward) remains ambiguous nonetheless.

Aziz Said employs the chronotope "Vaqt manzili" (The Destination of Time) in service of purpose and ideational intention; time devoted to a specific destination determines the action's main and important direction. The boundary of "ikki ming yil" (two thousand years) fully encompasses the fate of tribe-clan-people-nation; trust in the will of Truth—"barcha tilsimot, sir-asror, savollarga javoblar sohibi"

(the possessor of all mysteries, secrets, and answers to questions)—emphasizes the path of humanity through the strength of faith and belief; in the core of the lyrical hero's feeble striving toward essence is reflected the relationship between servant and God Almighty:

va men vaqt oldingami, orqagami oqayotganini
 aniq bilguvchini izlab zir yugurar
 va ko'zlarim hayratdan
 va yuragim dahshatdan muzga
 aylanayotganini tuyar [3:11].

(and I would run searching for one who knows exactly / whether time flows forward or backward / and I would feel my eyes from wonder / and my heart from terror turning / to ice.)

In the text, each stroke gives imagination a certain direction, yet uneven depiction does not ensure logical consistency. At the center of consciousness's illumination, expression taking bold steps transforms philosophy into art, creating the possibility of hearing melody and the need to know the subject of life. Whereas "the modern artist does not speak about the unexpressed but points to it, he attempts to express what cannot be understood, he narrates about things in their language, he does not learn to depict the world but tries to forget himself and merge with it" [4:125]. The inevitable ideational dominance aims to lead the reader into a unique spiritual world; in the current situation, harmony creatively emancipates expression. In fact, a connection exists between individual, nature and society; this connection fulfills the task of bonding cooperative relationships together:

va so'nggi xabarchi Muhammad alayhissalom
 tashrifidan
 va unga Qur'oni karim tushirilganidan
 va Qazodan
 va Qadardan

va Lavhul-Mahfuzdan

va shaytoni laindan

va aslim ruhligidan

va vujudim ruhga idishligidan [3:17].

(and from the arrival of the last messenger Muhammad peace be upon him / and from the revelation of the Holy Quran to him / and from Divine Decree / and from Divine Destiny / and from the Preserved Tablet / and from the cursed Satan / and from my origin being spiritual / and from my existence being a vessel for the soul.)

In the text, the author reveals inner reproaches through the realism of historical psychology; the mediation of the external world does not limit the creator's nature but rather displays the signs of poetic skill. The connection between moment and eternity tests the direction of human will; words that do not fit into concepts prepare ground for understanding symbols. Throughout the text, the poet points to important details, attempting to reveal the essence of astronomical units. The path leading to emotional cognition generalizes the philosophical depth of problems that occupy human consciousness.

In general, in Aziz Said's poem "Vaqt manzili" (The Destination of Time), the artistic idea becomes a factor ensuring emotional impact; a complete impression built on the pedestal of the author's ideal intensifies aesthetic value. Meditative contemplation places life and imagination side by side in the philosophy of genuine creativity, grafting metaphor onto expression. In poetic interpretation, the creator blends comparison, proportion, analogy, description and analysis, transferring symbol from concept to the crucible of thought. The narrator, who created the possibility for comparison, perfects historical evidence in creative worldview; the mixed method of narration prepares ground for gathering the psychology of depiction to a specific point. In it, the discipline of expression and depiction creates content from form, centralizing meaning.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2023.
2. Adabiyot nazariyasi. Ikki jildlik, 1-jild. –Toshkent: Fan, 1978.
3. Aziz Said. Vaqt manzili. – Toshkent: Akademnashr, 2021.
4. Jahon adiblari adabiyot haqida. - Toshkent: Ma'naviyat, 2010.
5. Quronov D. Adabiyot nazariyasi asoslari. - Toshkent: Akademnashr, 2018.
6. <http://www.ziyouz.com/>.